

THE STRUCTURE AND TYPES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE IN TEACHING

Sarsenbaev Ramazan Janabay uli

PhD student at NDPI

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Annotation: This article explores the concept of psychological and pedagogical competence, focusing on its various dimensions and types. It examines both foreign and domestic approaches to defining competence in education, highlighting social, special, individual, and extreme professional competencies. The article further delves into A.K. Markova's and N.V. Kuzmina's classifications, which emphasize the teacher's ability to apply specialized knowledge, methods, and communication skills in pedagogy. Additionally, it underscores the importance of methodological competence and the teacher's self-reflection, offering insights into the formation and modeling of psychological and pedagogical competence in higher education.

Key words: socio-psychological competence, differential psychological competence, teacher's professional development, pedagogical activity, modeling competence, psychological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается понятие психолого-педагогической компетентности, акцентируя внимание на ее различных измерениях и типах. В ней рассматриваются как зарубежные, так и отечественные подходы к определению компетентности в образовании, выделяются социальные, специальные, индивидуальные и экстремальные профессиональные компетенции. Далее в статье подробно рассматриваются классификации А.К.Марковой и Н.В.Кузьминой, в которых подчеркивается способность учителя применять в педагогике специальные знания, методы и коммуникативные навыки. Кроме того, подчеркивается важность методической компетентности и саморефлексии преподавателя, что дает представление о формировании и моделировании психолого-педагогической компетентности в высшем образовании.

Ключевые слова: социально-психологическая компетентность, дифференциальная психологическая компетентность, профессиональное развитие педагога, педагогическая деятельность, моделирующая компетентность, психологические знания, педагогические знания.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada psixologik-pedagogik kompetentlik tushunchasi o'rganilib, uning turli o'lchamlari va turlariga e'tibor qaratilgan.

Unda ta'limda kompetensiyani aniqlashning xorijiy va mahalliy yondashuvlari o'rganilib, ijtimoiy, maxsus, individual va ekstremal kasbiy kompetensiyalar ajratib ko'rsatilgan. Maqolada A.K.Markova va N.V.Kuzminaning ta'riflari yanada chuqurroq o'rganilgan bo'lib, ularda o'qituvchining pedagogikada maxsus bilim, metod va muloqot ko'nikmalarini qo'llash qobiliyatiga urg'u berilgan. Bundan tashqari, oliy ta'limda psixologik-pedagogik kompetentlikni shakllantirish va modellashtirish bo'yicha tushunchalarni taqdim etib, uslubiy kompetentlik va o'qituvchining o'z-o'zini aks ettirishi muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-psixologik kompetentlik, differensial psixologik kompetentlik, o'qituvchining kasbiy rivojlanishi, pedagogik faoliyat, modellashtirish kompetentligi, psixologik bilim, pedagogik bilim.

When considering the essence of psychological and pedagogical competence, we turned to dictionaries and scientific studies that provide an integral characteristic that to some extent reflects all modern approaches to defining competence.

In foreign professional pedagogy, when defining competence, the emphasis is placed on the specialist's ability to act independently and responsibly. The main types of professional competence are:

- social competence as the ability to group activities and cooperation with others, willingness to take responsibility for the results of one's work, mastery of professional training methods;

“special competence” - readiness to independently perform specific types of activities, the ability to solve typical professional tasks and evaluate the results of one's work, the ability to independently acquire new knowledge and skills in one's specialty;

- individual competence - readiness for constant professional development and self-realization in professional work, the ability for professional reflection, overcoming professional crises and deformities (1).

A.K. Markova identifies another type of competence - extreme professional competence, which implies the ability to act in suddenly complicated conditions. (2, p. 35).

In our point of view, the problem of professional pedagogical competence is considered by modern researchers in accordance with the tradition of analyzing the teacher's qualities, which are important for their successful professional activity, established in domestic pedagogical science. Currently, many researchers include in the concept of professional pedagogical competence the

knowledge and skills necessary for carrying out multifaceted educational and upbringing activities.

Today, pedagogy and psychology, as well as other sciences dealing with the problems of higher education, believe that competence is the basis for the successful work of a teacher, including a higher school teacher.

In modern pedagogy, professional-pedagogical competence is understood as an integrative quality of the individual, representing the most adequate, proportional set of professional, communicative, and personal qualities of the teacher, contributing to achieving high-quality results in the learning and upbringing process.

A.K. Markova's concept of pedagogical competence includes all the pedagogical personality traits that ensure a high result in professional activity. To expand the content of this concept, the author includes in it, in addition to pedagogical activity itself, pedagogical communication, as well as the subjective properties of the teacher (3).

Researchers rightly highlight the various types of a teacher's professional competence.

N.V. Kuzmina's classification is based on the fact that the concept of professional-pedagogical competence focuses on the representation of the teacher as a subject of pedagogical influence, capable of structuring scientific and practical knowledge in a special way in order to better solve pedagogical tasks. The main types of professional-pedagogical competence according to N.V. Kuzmina are:

1. Specialized competence in the field of the subject being taught.
2. Methodological competence in the field of methods for forming students' knowledge and skills.
3. Social and psychological competence in the field of communication processes.
4. Differential psychological competence in the field of motives, abilities, orientation of students.
5. Autopsychological competence in the area of merits and disadvantages of one's own activity (4).

A teacher's special competence presupposes their high authority as a scientist, as a representative of a particular science. It includes knowledge, awareness, knowledge of a specific science, its methodology, current state and development prospects. This type of competence also includes the ability to apply scientific knowledge, using it as a tool for influencing students.

The methodological competence of the university teacher is aimed at effectively organizing the pedagogical process and creating new teaching technologies.

Socio-psychological competence is closely linked to the culture of pedagogical communication and the general style of professional behavior of the teacher. It is precisely they that allow him to build his communication with different categories of students in different ways, achieving necessary changes in the system of their orientation, professional readiness, and competence.

A teacher's differential-psychological competence manifests itself in their ability to build the learning process taking into account the individual characteristics of students. To engage each student in active work not only on studying the subject, but also on themselves as a future professional and creative person, the teacher requires knowledge of the psychology of personality and the psychology of activity, mastery of pedagogical research methods.

A teacher's autopsychological competence lies in knowing themselves as a professional, being able to make adjustments to their activities and communication, taking into account their strengths and weaknesses. The high level of this type of competence is manifested in the teacher's ability to take the position of a researcher in relation to themselves, their activities, and their results.

Methodological competence among various types of pedagogical competence occupies one of the leading positions. It to a certain extent integrates the entire system of special scientific, psychological, pedagogical knowledge and skills and has a clearly expressed applied character. Today, a truly competent teacher can be called one who has an extensive system of knowledge, has his own individual style of activity.

Therefore, the essence of psychological and pedagogical competence lies in the systematic unity of the teacher's psychological and pedagogical knowledge, experience, and qualities that allow for effective pedagogical activity, purposeful organization of pedagogical communication processes, as well as the teacher's personal development and improvement.

The insufficient development of a number of aspects of postgraduate education, the growing relevance, the theoretical and practical significance of its provisions, require defining the forms and methods of forming a teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence based on modeling its structure.

Modeling, in the broadest sense of the term, is understood as "researching objects of cognition on their models; constructing and studying models of real

objects and phenomena, clarifying the properties of any object, process or phenomenon, i.e. its model, as well as for predicting phenomena of interest to the researcher” (5, p.393). In pedagogy, the point of view of G.M. Andreeva is increasingly recognized, which suggests that the concept of “model” should be considered as a system whose research serves as a means of obtaining information about another system (6). The theorists in the field of modeling emphasize that models in all cases act as analogies of research objects, that is, they are similar, but not identical to the latter

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